

On the Pythagorean Cipher, the Seven Concealment Tricks, and the Underlying Language of Voynich Manuscript

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Abstract.

For nearly six centuries, the decipherment of Voynich Manuscript has baffled scholars and cryptologists. None of the previous attempts succeeded to find out the used coding method in this manuscript; hence, scholars called it the most mysterious book in the world. This work, therefore, explains the design of its cipher and identifies its underlying language. It demonstrates the mathematical idea and the method of “design by addition” that an anonymous proficient designer has used in order to create over hundred glyphs, using strokes, circles, and half circles. It proves that this designer used Pythagoras theorem to create glyphs so that each denotes numerically the rank of a specific letter in *Abjd* (*Abjad*) alphabet of Sinai, from one to twenty-eight. It shows as well that, in handwriting, the designer used seven tricks as additional measures in order to conceal the geometric cipher and the encoded language. Then, it proves that the underlying language of the manuscript is a medieval vernacular dialect close to the hybrid Urdu and/or Hindi of Hindustan. It demonstrates as well the transliteration of some of its words and sentences, using Perso-Arabic, Roman, and Devanāgarī scripts, in addition to the English translation. The translated sentences hint to that the text is a poetic chatter like a diary written by the —educated grandsons of the— Gypsies who had emigrated from Hindustan to Persia, Armenia, Levant, Egypt, or Greece between the 7th and 14th centuries CE, and then emigrated to Germany and other countries in Europe at the beginning of the 15th century CE.

Keywords: Voynich Manuscript, MS-408, VMS, Idris, Hermes, Pythagoras, cipher, Hindustan, Urdu, Hindi, Gypsies, Roma, Zott, Jats.

1. Introduction.

The Voynich Manuscript (VMS) is a 15th century codex (Layfield *et al*, 2020), where in 2009, the result of carbon-14 dating experiment showed that its leather-parchments were produced between 1404 and 1438 CE (Zyats *et al*, 2012; Zandbergen, 2016). The digital numbering, from f.1r to f.116v, of the digitized copy of VMS¹ demonstrate that it originally had 232 pages of various sizes, and twenty-eight pages of which are missing (Davis, 2020); but without deciphering the coding method, this does not confirm that the current VMS’s text is incomplete. Almost ninety percent of the remained pages contain colored illustrations with handwritten text. Most illustrations are sketches of plants that might be medical, anesthetic, or just fictional portraits (e.g., f.2v); some were drawn in a surreal way, which depict plant leafs as silhouette of birds (e.g. f.56r) and roots of plants as imaginary marine-creatures, animals, or human faces (e.g. f.55v, f.90v, & f.101v). VMS contains as well diagrams that seem similar to the astrological and astronomical charts in medieval esoteric books (e.g., f.67r), sketches of naked

¹ See the online digital copy of VMS at (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/pdfs/2002046.pdf>).

women disport in what look like natural lakes down a waterfall or rainy zippers, or in constructed reservoirs on a water stream (f.75r), fictional flying bathtubs (f.82r), and few men (e.g., f.66r & f.80r). In few pages we also see rough sketches of animals such as pangolin (f.80v), serpent (f.49r), horse, deer, jackal, komodo dragon, giant catfish (f.79v), eagle (f.86v), and dragon (f.25v), as well as what looks like an elf or a statue below a blue rose (f.102r). The folded page f.85v-f.86r demonstrates what appears as an imaginary schematic site-plan of a group of castles and temples in a mountainous area with cardinal directions and a text, in the southern corner, written in a spiral form similar to the ancient technique of writing the spiritual sentences in Hermetic sciences. This page also shows the use of the architecture technique of façade and axonometric rotation—in the projection plan—in different directions, the free-hand presentation technique of contour lines and floor of the outdoor spaces, accurate parallel grid, and sunrise/sunset during the equinoxes, which indicates that it was produced by an architect, may be knowledgeable in spherical astronomy. Moreover, the geometric representation of the correlation between the basic numeric codes (7, 12, and 13) along the east-south/north-west direction and the spiral text in this particular page indicates that he studied too the ancient mathematical linguistics of Hermes Trismegistus, the most famous architectonic master in the ancient world. He also symbolized the direction of north with a small circle around a triangular glyph from an ancient list of secret writing scripts, which indicates that he might have studied *Sīmiyā σημεία*, i.e., spiritual writings (see Al-Simāwī², 1260 CE, pp.41-46). In addition to this, in page f.78r, the painter illustrated the words of revelation—like angels' whispering—from what look like two upper celestial jewels³, in the form of plane numeric matrixes transformed into hollow cylinders, which indicates that he knew the ancient concepts of the architectonic—topological—characteristics of the celestial language. The sequence of illustrations in VMS directs the mind to unproved hypothesis regarding that it discusses diverse subjects grouped in separate sections; there are many opinions regarding this hypothesis, for instance, outside the framework of any intended spiritual scenario, Bauer (1917, p.8) said, it is possible that the pictures are not actually related to the text. Yet, in terms of creativity, and from the metaphysical perspective, the surreal pun technique used by the painter depicts the latent spirit in each botanical element presented in the artwork to incarnate—in the botanical realm—perhaps part of the philosophy of Socrates in dialogue *Phaedo* (Plato, 330a BCE). Alternatively, it may be an incarnation of part of the secret philosophy of divination—using seeds of plants—in some ancient cultures in Africa and Mesoamerica, e.g., Maya. In the eye of any literate painter and student of the ancient metaphysical philosophies, the illustrations in general—with the like chemical bottles in, e.g., page f.88r—would give the impression that it might discuss spiritual practices and the relevant cures and advices. It may be similar to the instructions that are usually included without pictures of plants or humans in medieval esoteric books that show as well the desirable actions in the course of time (Al-Buni, 1226 CE, p.218, & p.363). The illustration in page f.77v seems veterinary, and similar to other scenes, it perhaps narrates a dream like scenario, where the figure at the top of the page depicts what looks like the anatomy of part of a rare goat with three breasts. Maybe it is about goat milk and its diverse benefits and use as a medical cure by the nomadic shepherds.

A set of contents with seductive illustrations that make it looks tempting to be acquired, with expensive price, in the eyes of many people before the era of imprinting, informatics, and internet. Without decoding the cipher, no one can affirm which information the manuscript includes: scientific theories, fictional narratives, or obscure traditions; nor can confirm what type of text is this: prose, verse, or magical spells; and no one knows yet who wrote it. However, there is partly reliable information about

²- The book cover is missing, but the author mentioned his name in page 26, and correct publication date may be during the 13th century.

³- The imaginary ancient concept of the upper celestial jewels—of the ethereal side of nature—is explained in section 2 (see footnote 8).

some of those who interacted with its contents mentally, sensorically, or spiritually and kept it in their possessions during this long period, until Wilfrid Voynich purchased it from the Jesuit library in Rome in 1912; and it was named after him ever since. From among the previous owners (see, Robinson, 2016), the first known buyer (in 1599 CE) was Rudolf II, Holy Roman Emperor (Guzy, 2022) and the last known student of this cipher manuscript (in 1666 CE) was the Jesuit polymath Athanasius Kircher (Steele, 1928). Perhaps all interested researchers, and the author too (from the first look in a news in January 13, 2023), cannot deny that there is something unusual in VMS —like mirage— that attracts the mind to approach it in order to investigate its identity and contents; at least the artistic design of its glyphs. Since 1969, it has been kept in Yale University's Beinecke rare books and manuscripts library, with a catalog number MS-408 (Robinson, 2016). All attempts by experts during the 20th century, including those by known code-breakers from WWI and WW2 (e.g., William Friedman, Elizabeth Friedman, Prest Currier, John Tillman) and their supporting teams were not successful to find out the used coding method in VMS (D'Imperio, 1978); yet, they produced comprehensive studies on this enigmatic conundrum. Currier's (1976) findings are the most notable, where he concluded that more than one scribe wrote the text and perhaps there are two different underlying languages in VMS. During the last two decades, arrays of researches have been published on the topic too, which included advanced computer analyses, diverse claims, and some interesting findings; yet, none has demonstrated a discussion, or formulated conclusions based on the true coding method of VMS. Some scholars concluded that VMS is, or may be, a hoax, i.e., it was not produced by encoding of a human language (e.g., Whitfield, 2003; Rugg, 2004; Schinner, 2007; Rugg & Taylor, 2017) and its text is statistically similar to human produced samples of meaningless text (Gaskell & Bower, 2022). Other works showed statistical proofs indicate that the characteristics of VMS's text resemble that of the human languages (e.g., Landini, 2001; Bower & Lindemann, 2021) and five scribes participated in writing the text (Davis, 2020 & 2022). All published or announced hypotheses⁴ regarding the underlying language of VMS were not based on decoding its true cipher; hence, no one has provided the correct decoding method for transliterating the whole set of almost 110 glyphs in VMS. Regarding the encoded script, from among the published researches, one explanation was found consistent with the second result of the present work, which relied on analyzing the text by computer. That is, regarding the results of determining what might be vowels, and their locations, in the words of VMA, Reddy and Knight (2011) pointed out that a more likely explanation, of the results, is that the script is an *Abjd* (*Abjad*). Yet, their conclusion hints to that —*Abjd* system and— VMA's text do not contain vowels, which may not be true.

In fact, VMS was written using special forms of glyphs that, despite the use of advanced computer analysis operations, formed a strong and unexpected barrier against identifying its underlying language. The reason most likely concerns the obscure image which seems latent behind designing the contents of VMS and the related ancient mathematical linguistics that the designer of its glyphs seem was aware about and used it to create the coding method of VMS's text. Unless the encryption was for hiding some obscure traditions, this situation may call for thinking that in this esoteric realm, especially in the medieval and pre-Renaissance eras, the primary purpose of VMS may have two sides. It has a deceptive goal and a noble goal in the same time. The first targets the treasure of physical gold and the latter targets the treasure of lost knowledge. Even if the deceptive side was for selling nothing more than gibberish, the noble side is probably there in the form of a decipherment competition throughout the time. The evidence of the noble side is written in VMS, as will be demonstrated in section-3 herein below, which may have unforeseen purpose and benefit, e.g., cultural, ideological, socio-economic, and/or developmental. Therefore, this work primarily deals with the noble side in order to show the

⁴- See for instance the hypotheses of Bax, Hauer, Kondark, Gibbs, & Cheshire in the review of Bower & Lindemann (2021).

method of designing the glyphs of VMS and then to identify its underlying language. Discussing what the full text of VMS contains is outside the scope of this work. Just the translation of about 120 words and 5 sentences from different pages will be discussed in order to show the reliable evidences regarding its underlying language. Whatever the scientific, literary, or cultural value of VMS's text can be, which will be partly highlighted hereinafter, this work may indirectly enable some readers and researchers to find out logical answers to the question why it was difficult to determine its underlying language with computer analyses.

2- Basic principles of Hermes Trismegistus's geometrical and mathematical linguistics.

As a kind of ancient faith belief, most of, if not all, what have been published in different eras about the applications of secret ancient Egyptian mathematical linguistics of Hermes Trismegistus have been intentionally formulated in a general or unclear way or lack the proper sequence to mislead only the readers whom the basic principles are not in their minds. Taking into account the diverse scientific backgrounds, abilities, and accumulated knowledge of the authors, works like “Monas Hieroglyphica” by Dee (1564 CE) and “the Theater of Terrestrial Astronomy” by Kelly (1667 CE) are examples of the Renaissance writings in Europe on such topics. Besides, the publications by some medieval authors included local applications that —mathematically— cannot be applied on all human tongues, which unfortunately led to forgetting many of the basic principles, especially those related to the musical scale. Many writers did not study the sciences of the Pyramids builders; hence, they misunderstood the concept of architecture of letters, words, and sentences in any human language, which form the basics for understanding the celestial language. Consequently, the translation of books that lack the basic principles into other languages led modern writers to write about the topic —and the related philosophy— from a general or historical perspective. The review of D’Imperio (1978, pp.52-64) on “Medieval and Renaissance Cosmology and Iconography” demonstrates cited similar publications on the topic. For the sake of this work and perhaps other future researches on VMS's text, this section discusses in a simple informative way the ancient concept of the architecture of letters and words and the related celestial codes.

In history, one of the basic principles of the ancient Egyptian architectonic philosophy and mathematical linguistics of Idris (Al-Buni⁵, 1226 CE, p.370) is the use of numbers to denote the alphabetical letters. It was known in ancient Egypt and in lands of the nations that have used *Abjd* alphabet of the ancient tribes of Sinai (Al-Maqrizi, 1442 CE, vol.1, p.525) and those who lived around the Golf of Arabia⁶, which was also spread to other regions. Following Aboufotouh’s (2017a) method on how to pronounce and read the sequence of glyphs in the ancient Egyptian texts, Idris is the spiral pronunciation sequence of the cartouche of king Ratoisês⁷ *Ρατοίσης* (Manetho, 3rd century CBE, p.46). He was also known as Hermes Trismegistus that the Greeks identified as Thoth (Manetho, 3rd century BCE, p.209; Chambers, 1882, p.vii; Ebeling, 2007, pp.45-48; & Von Stuckrad, 2009, p.55), the developer of —priestly— writing according to Socrates in dialogue Phaedrus (Plato, 330 BCE-b). The cartouche of Idris or Idras (Her-m = the great and

⁵- See a copy of Al-Buni’s book in Arabic at (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/catalog/32304220>); and there are some attempts to translate the book into other languages, see for example the Spanish translation of some parts of the book by Cordero, J. C. at (<https://archive.org/details/al-buni/page/368/mode/lup>).

⁶- Erythraean *Ἐρυθρὴν* Sea (Herodotus, 484-425 BCE, p.282), which is now called the Red Sea.

⁷-The Greek’s linear-sequence with “es”, that in modern time, most Egyptologists pronounce it wrongly as *Khafre* (Aboufotouh, 2022). He was the grandson of king Suphis-i *Σούφις*, the founder of the 4th Dynasty (Manetho, 3rd cn CBE, p.46) and the Architectonic master of the Pyramids builders.

supported by the falcon spirit, where “*es*” is Greek) was found in the tomb of G4970 in the pyramids plateau (see fig.3 in, Lehner, 2012, p.114).

In his mathematical linguistics that deals with the hidden geometry of letters, words, and sentences, and their relationship with the material and ethereal sides of nature, each letter has two numeric values. In history, the basic principles of this ancient Egyptian science were used, for instance, to create words and sentences with strong spiritual influence, to design scripts or numeric symbols, and/or to create multiple types of ciphers for private or scientific uses. It was believed —without published scientific proofs— that it could enable the acquainted priests and philosophers to understand and develop diverse numeric methods —and the related laboratory inventions— to communicate with the immortal ethereal creatures. The mathematics of Hermes Trismegistus, Pyramids Builders, and the Egyptian Harpedonaptae was advanced to the extent that they have used relativistic equations in pyramids design, which look similar —in structure and complexity— to the equations of time dilation by Lorentz and Einstein in Special Relativity (see, e.g., Aboufotouh, 2022 & 2015).

The two numeric values were used to interpret words (and ideal sentences) into numeric codes or vice versa. Each code can be represented spatially by basic or complex geometric forms, where some of which were also used in architecture and site planning. The idea is quite similar to modern topology in the sense that each numeric-code can be interpreted into diverse geometric forms; where for instance, in topology, a square sheet of paper —with a length 7 units— can be turned into a cylinder 7 units high. The philosophy of this ancient science differentiates between what is eternal and what is temporary and changing in the realm of human languages and systems of writing. It primarily deals with the numeric codes of words —starting from the roots of two letters— and not their meanings in the material side of nature that can change, from one tongue to another, or may be forgotten and die over time. These codes were considered the bricks of all languages and the link between all human tongues and the celestial language of the ethereal side of nature. It is like, for instance, the relationship between the binary codes and the computer system— and its various platforms and translation software— where in this manmade model, the computer represents the planetary system. Hence, theoretically, each celestial code —in the spectrum of real numbers— can be converted into an array of correct numeric matrixes that —with some natural and manmade auxiliary factors— can travel in space like waves and carry the communication messages to the upper jewels⁸ —that form the servers— of the system. This imaginary mechanism was thought of as part of virtual physics that govern the ethereal side of nature; and the design of the relevant applications seems to depend on the DNA waves. The scripts that visually denote the celestial codes and the corresponding words, in any tongue, are changing and not eternal. This is because, in design principles, using diverse design methods and concepts, hundred proficient designers can create hundred different forms for each letter in only one alphabet.

The first numeric value, and influentially intrinsic, is the rank (collation) of each letter in *Abjd* sequence that contains 28 uncompounded letters, where *A,b,j,d* (or *A,b,g,d*) are the first four letters in the sequence. *Abjd* ranks have multiple types of interpretation related to the domain of use. For instance, in simple geometry, each *Abjd* rank can be interpreted as the number of uniform intervals that a letter denotes on the scale from one to twenty-eight units, as the 28 mean-fingers of the ancient Egyptian

⁸- The term “upper jewels” is a metaphor used by medieval writers (e.g., Al-Maqrizi, 1364–1442 CE, Pyramids section) to express what resemble the powerful ethereal servers in the ethereal information network of the solar system or of the plant Earth. It was believed that it is a coherent part of the ethereal side of nature —as sources of cosmic knowledge— and that was used by the Pyramids Builders. The concept is perhaps similar to the modern internet servers of the worldwide web in the material side of nature.

royal cubit⁹. In the multi-dimensional celestial-space, each *Abjd* rank can also be interpreted as a vector, number of cycles, or time intervals; hence, it represents the assigned hidden power of the letter. The second numeric value is known, in the mind of many people, as *Abjd* (*Abjad*) values in an abstract way. However, in the ancient realm of mathematical and geometric linguistics, it is the circular travel distance that each of the 28 letters implies on the scale, of variable intervals, from one to a thousand arc degrees (Al-Buni, 1226 CE).

To understand the relationship between the two values of each letter in the realm of spherical astronomy, we can imagine that each letter represents —a geometric model of— a celestial system composed of a terrestrial planet and its only moon that together rotate around their parent star. In this system, the rank is the number of cycles that this moon performs around its planet during the travel-distance of its planet in orbit around their parent star, in arc degrees. For instance, in the system that represents the first letter, the moon performs one cycle around its planet per each 1° in orbit (i.e., which could be written as ^{1c}a₁°), and in the system that represents the last letter, the moon performs 28 cycles around its planet per each 1000° in orbit, i.e., 2 orbits and 280° (i.e., ^{28c}gh₁₀₀₀°). These celestial codes can also be written as ^{1a}a₁, ..., ^{28g}gh₁₀₀₀ or just 1₁, ..., 28₁₀₀₀. From this perspective, the rank is the system-code and the orbital distance is the travel-code. This is the first principle of the dynamic architecture of words based on imagining that each *Abjd* letter is part of a planetary system's configuration plan. Many of those who wrote about this topic, or have tried to develop it for the best —from their point of view— were not aware about the system-code and its use. Nor they were aware about its relationship with the travel-code. Most writers talked only about the use of *Abjd* values (travel-codes) for encoding in an abstract way.

Moreover, creating sacred words and spiritual sentences is like, for instance, the fusion of natural elements (e.g., Hydrogen and its isotopes, namely: ¹H, ²H, ³H, ..., to ²⁸H if existed) to create a precious element (like gold or platinum). Or merging numerals to create ideal system-codes that are sacred like perfect numbers (Euclid, 150 BCE, propos. 36, pp.277-278) but with using different equations. Ideal codes are related to frequencies of the musical tones, e.g., form La# major of the second musical octave (117 Hz/s) —the first black key in all pianos— up to that of the musical octave that approaches the infinity¹⁰. There are also the unique codes. For instance, merging the 3rd and 4th *Abjd* ranks (^{3j}₃ with ^{4d}₄) creates the unique root ^{12j}₇, which means a scale in ancient Egypt. The two numbers 12 & 7 —in the imaginary celestial code 12₇— are the result of multiplication and addition¹¹, respectively; it is the first and the most ancient unique-code. Notice that this merging process denotes the relationship between two unique numbers: 12 and 7, and their many ancient uses, e.g.: (i) as intervals of time, and (ii) the 12 half notes in a musical octave, and its sets of 7 harmonic notes. In spherical and simple geometry, ^{12j}₇ represents a rectangular plane, like the ancient Egyptian rectangle 3*4 units (Aboufotouh, 2012), that sailed seven arc degrees in orbit, or rotated 7° on the perimeter of a circle in an Euclidean space. Similarly, merging ^{2b}₂ with ¹⁴ⁿ₅₀ creates the root ^{28b}_{n₁₀₀} (i.e., 28₁₀₀), which is a unique code that means a perfect pyramidal structure¹² in Ancient Egypt. The geometric representations of celestial codes —such as ideal, sacred, unique, normal, and/or their corresponding travel codes— start from the space of two-damns up to the space of multi-dimensions. During the current precession cycle of our blue planet earth, humans may have assigned, and still can assign, diverse meanings for roots like *jd* and *bn*

⁹- See the design of the royal cubit in (Aboufotouh, 2015).

¹⁰- The frequency 7-8 Hz/s of the Human brain's perception, is the La# major of four octaves below 117 Hz/s (the frequency of the first musical note in pianos); discussing the equations of the ideal codes is outside the scope of this work.

¹¹- In merging system letters, we multiply the ranks and we sum the travel distances. Where addition implies increasing the momentum in orbit and multiplication implies encoding the repeated cycles that are recorded in different frames-of-time in the memory of the merged system.

¹²- See the structure of the pyramidal complex system of the perfect number 28 (C_{S28} or C_{S24+4}) in (Aboufotouh, 2004).

—or their equivalents *dj* and *nb*, respectively— and can write, or may have written, them using diverse scripts and with diverse vowel diacritics. For instance, in medieval Arabic, *jd* (or *gd*) means grandpa or working hard; and *bn* means son of or to build. One can find different meanings in other languages for all the possible roots (and words) for each celestial code, from 2_3 (*ab* or *ba*) to as much as one can write and read.

Similar to the concept of music of the spheres, based on using the long ideal codes, each created spiritual sentence could be written on the circumference of circles similar to orbits or as texts in spiral forms, which may look like the design of the Phaistos Disc. Generally, spiritual sentences may sound like poetry and usually have no grammar, related to any known human language, but should have ideal hidden-architectures in the space-time. The related ancient mathematical and geometric linguistics never was part of the frontier of science in any era, and it was only known to the acquainted and qualified fellows of Hermes Trismegistus School of Architectonic Philosophy, such as the acquainted High priests of Egypt, Solomon, Pythagoras, Plato, and other philosophers or multi-disciplinary researchers. There is only general information about it —such as Plato’s method for interpreting the travel-codes and Solomon’s ideal codes— mentioned by few conservative medieval writers (e.g., Al-Buni, 1226 CE).

In this ancient math, the sequence of *Abjd* alphabet was considered God-made, celestially related¹³, sacred, and the base to generate other compound letters and words (with diverse diacritics) in many, if not all the languages of humans that have been naturally generated and collectively developed during the current precession cycle of our planet. Besides, *Abjd* sequence comprises two parts (ranges). The first is the large part that forms the whole range of 28 ranks (letters), which is called the *a-gh* range. The second is the small part that includes the first 22 ranks (letters), which is called the *a-t* range. The ratio between the two ranges is¹⁴ approximately $4/\pi$. The two ranges are comprised from, or can generate arrays of sub-ranges or sub-sets (chapters) from 3 to 28 ranks that to which the roots of particular language belong, or can be found using diverse methods, either from the base subset or from the correlated long sequence(s). The sequence of letters in each used root is therefore correlated, which is the product of natural and/or designed methods. Some of these base sub-sets are related to, or include, some animal sounds (e.g. subset 6-16 that includes wolf howling *a'w*); and there is, also, the subset of the syllables of the seven harmonic notes of the musical octave (i.e., subset 4-20 of *dosikolamefara*¹⁵). The created sequences from each subset reveal the identity of the hidden architecture of the corresponding words. In addition, one of the simple methods for creating the long sequence from each subset is similar to creating a row comprises the sequence of the six musical half-tones of all modes of the hexatonic musical scale¹⁶ (in two directions, clockwise and anticlockwise). Using other complex methods, see (Al-Buni, 1226 CE, p.365), one can generate the long sequence of the largest set that would comprise more than half a million letters ($28*28*2*360$), which can be written in 720 pages.

¹³- The term celestially related here implies that the 28 system-letters might correlate to the 28 harmonic intervals of the size of the solar system’s equatorial plane, starting from the orbit of Mercury up to 192 AU, see the Architectonic Law of Music of the Spheres in (Aboufotouh, 2004).

¹⁴- It is similar to the ratio between the times of the precession and obliquity cycles of our planet, according to the encoded information by Pyramids Builders (Aboufotouh, 2015).

¹⁵- The chapter of *dosikolamefara* is unpublished study by the author of this work; as there is no known previous publication correlates the syllable names of the musical tones to the subset 4-20 in *Abjd* sequence of *Sinai*, see for instance *Solmization* at (<https://www.britannica.com/art/solmization#ef259081>). In this regard, as mention in Description de l’Egypt (1809-1828), the Egyptians used to write the 12 half tones, using *Abjd* ranks from 1 to 12.

¹⁶- See the modes of the hexatonic musical scale at (<https://ianring.com/musictheory/scales/1197>); for instance, using the subset 1-13, the 1st mode of *Abjd* ranks, is 1,3,4,6,8,11; and 2nd mode is 2,4,5,7,9,12 and so on.

The idea is quite similar to the correlation between the names of the standard genetic codes and the naturally generated long sequence by the set of four bases of DNA (*a, c, t, and g*), in the double helix.

Taking into consideration that each letter may have diverse pronunciations with vowel diacritics (according to the human tongue), all cases of the same letter have the same two-numeric-values. During the life of humanity, some nations and civilizations used either of the two ranges of *Abjd* sequence with diverse pronunciations; other nations changed the positions of various letters, omitted some letters, or created additional compounded letters as well as created diverse forms of scripts and diacritical marks in order to confirm their mechanical or organic solidarity. Yet, today, in some alphabets that are written with different script and even pronounced differently, we can notice the letters that did remain in the original positions. For instance, in English alphabet, the letters *a, b, c, d,...*, *k, l, m*, and *n* keep their original ranks as in ancient *Abjd* sequence of Sinai, i.e., 1, 2, 3, 4,...,11, 12, 13, and 14, respectively.

Therefore, the authentic *Abjd* ranks and the corresponding travel distances were, and can be, dealt with as the base linguistic index for —mapping the letters and— generating the equivalent celestial codes for the roots —and the corresponding words— of all languages that have been created, or will be created, by the earthlings at any specific point in time, until the day of extinction¹⁷. In this regard, in mapping other alphabets to create the corresponding celestial codes, the position of all vowels in the *Abjd* sequence are the *Abjd* ranks 1, 5, 6, 10, and 16, where each position has diverse cases. Despite, that *Abjd* ranks 5 and 16 are not considered as long vowels in some languages like Arabic; the former is like the 5th letter *e* in English and the latter is like, e.g., the 1st letter *a* or the 15th letter *o* in English. Hence, in case of *o*, it will be shifted one position up; while *e* will remain as is. For instance, using Plato's method, in the outstanding metaphysical artwork "*Melencolia-I*", the gifted Renaissance painter Albrecht Dürer (1514 CE) from Nuremberg mapped eight *Abjd* ranks to their equivalents in Latin, where the meant beautiful travel-code 207 denotes *Mhlnkolia-I*. It is also relevant to the —hidden and sacred— celestial code ¹⁵⁶ALM₅₁ (or MAL). In the German mapping context, *Abjd* rank 11 "*k*" was moved eight positions back to be "*c*", while "*h*" became "*e*" as usual. Many of Dürer's art works indicate that maybe he was an acquainted fellow; and this indicates too that these methods were known in Germany perhaps before the Renaissance. In his treatise on the scripts of ancient languages, Al-Simawi (1260 CE) demonstrated the mapping of many alphabets —including the symbols of secret writings of Plato and other philosophers— with the *Abjd* sequence of Sinai. This perhaps may feed future researches on mapping —electronically— the list of roots and words of all human languages to their equivalents in the celestial language; and may feed, as well, advanced potential applications on other planetary systems that each may have different base linguistic index, perhaps according to the size of the system¹⁸. It is worth mentioning here that the hypotheses that some have created spiritual languages —such as the so-called Bālaybalan¹⁹— with special or mixed grammar in the past have no solid ground. It is incorrect to think that the old practices of mapping numerically the alphabet of any tongue with *Abjd* ranks in order to generate arrays of spiritual —and may be bizarre— sentences or words inserted in a working text that follows the grammar of that tongue could be considered as a kind of constructed language. The reason is that, in this realm, there is no need to create new language, because any letter, root, word, or even a sentence from any human language can be transformed into a celestial code, a geometric form, and a numeric matrix.

¹⁷- According to the Pyramids Builders, extinction (that might be complete or partial) will occur at the end of the current obliquity cycle (Aboulfotouh, 2014), which is nearly 15,600 Earth years from the Minor lunar stand-still of 2024-2025.

¹⁸- Hypothetically, it is from orbit of the first planet to boundary of the system (heliopause) by the interstellar space, which is correlated to size of the star.

¹⁹- See, for example, the article of Häberl (2015).

designer of VMS's glyphs was aware about the method of designing the hieratic numerals that was lately explained by Aboufotouh (2012), unless there was an unknown channel to disseminate the philosophy of the Egyptian mathematics to the country of the designer in ancient eras, but he certainly was aware about Pythagoras theorem. His designs indicate that he was acquainted in geometry, basic math, and apparently, he was aware too about the mathematical linguistics of Hermes Trismegistus, as part of the Architectonic Mathematics of pyramids builders. Hence, from his point of view, the coding method that he decided to use can be called the "Pythagorean Cipher", which is an "Expandable Geometric Substitution Cipher", EGSC. The term "Expandable" here implies that it has no limit, in terms of both the number of glyphs and the number of applications using diverse sequences of the alphabets of all human languages that was, currently exist, or will be created in the future until the day of extinction.

In handwriting, the designer, or the scribes, used seven tricks as additional security measures in order to conceal the geometric cipher and the underlying language. The first concealment trick is that the design elements that assemble the glyphs were not drawn in accurate proportions. Each element was rescaled to an appropriate size to create a consistent aesthetic shape and make the eye aware only about how many circles, half circles, or strokes are included in each letter's glyph in order to recognize its rank and identity. This smart-idea created additional security against quick decipherment, because the forms of some created glyphs became similar to the script of some known alphabets or numeral signs but have different pronunciation or meanings. This was done by rescaling (decrease or increase) the diameters of the circles (each implies 5) and half circles (each implies one) and using diverse lengths of vertical and horizontal strokes (each implies one). For instance, as shown in table.1, the glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 1 and 5 look like the letters *c* and *o* in Latin, respectively; and the glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 6, 10 and 11 look like the Arabic numerals 9, 8, and 2, respectively.

To read the ranks of the complex glyphs —that look like the ancient wooden-cranes of megalithic construction— in a quick way, we can count the vertical strokes from left to right, then count the horizontal strokes top-down, followed by counting the half circles, and finally, add the values of circles. The intersection of any two strokes does not imply splitting each one of them into two strokes. What has been taken into account is only the change of direction and not the intersection. The ranks of all glyphs used in the text of VMS are from 1 to 28. There are also few glyphs with higher numeric values, e.g., 61 (f.42v), which seem artistic and not alphabetical, and their meanings will be revealed with the complete translation of VMS; or perhaps, each was designed using *Abjd* travel-codes. Moreover, some glyphs in VMS denote similar ranks, which means that each of the corresponding letters has multiple pronunciations, such as *a*, *b*, *d*, *k*, and *y*. The designer also created —more than— 30 compound-glyphs (e.g., see table.2) that each combines two or three letters in one glyph form. Besides, eight of the 80 glyphs look like some *Sīmiyā* symbols, but their designs follow the same assembling method; only two of them were used in words, such as one of the cases of *Abjd* rank 21 (table.1). The remaining 6 glyphs may have been used in the 28 missing pages; and due to this limitation, their ranks were not verified, which were reckoned based on the assumption that each inclined stroke means ten. So far, the body of VMS's text was produced (written) using almost 74 glyphs and 30 compound glyphs, i.e., 104 glyphs in total. Table.2 shows the 110 glyphs of VMS. These glyphs are what have been found in VMS until the date of submitting this paper for publication; but there may be other glyphs have fallen inadvertently, particularly in drawings, and the reader can easily identify the rank and identity of each, using the above-mentioned method.

Regarding the noble side of the issue, in the left margin of page f.49v, the scribe wrote two columns. The 1st column comprised of a set of five Arabic numerals from 1 to 5 written top-down and linked to

a set of five glyphs (with ranks 5, 2, 6, 1, & 1, respectively) from the 26 glyphs in the 2nd column. As shown in fig.2, in the two sets, the total sum of either the five numerals, or the ranks of the five glyphs is 15; and 7 is the total sum of the 3rd and 4th values in both sets. Besides, the 2nd values are the same in the two sets, and the 1st and 5th values in the numeral set meet the 5th and 1st values in the set of 5 glyphs, respectively. The scribe also wrote the Arabic numeral 2 above the glyph of rank 2 in a word in page f.24v (table.3), which is the only case of using Arabic numerals in VMS's text; the other cases are found only in margins. The partial decoding key in fig.2 indicates that the designer did not have the intention to prevent strangers from breaking the cipher. On the contrary, he did it as a puzzle that could be solved by other fellows in order to start a long and exhausting journey in research to find out who wrote it and for what. This work is the first step in this long journey in order to reach the meant climax of the event, i.e., the moment of knowing the intended noble goal by VMS's writer if, and only if, this goal was really in the writer's mind. It is worth mentioning here that D'Imperio (1978, p.37) pointed out that the published works of Brumbaugh was based on the hypothesis that the sequences in the margins in f.r1, f.49v, f.66r, and f.76r; and in the 2nd ring in f.57v, as well as in the sequence in f.116v can provide aid in penetrating the cipher of VMS. Yet, unfortunately, his analyses —as demonstrated by D'Imperio— are irrelevant to the authentic ancient Egyptian mathematical linguistics of Hermes Trismegistus. Besides, all the ancient methods of designing the scripts of languages (human or celestial) should have been taken into consideration.

Links between the two sets	Set of 5 Numerals	Set of 5 Glyphs	
		Glyph	Rank
1 st No# meets the last glyph of rank 1	1	◦	5
2 nd No# meets the glyph of rank 2	2	⤿	2
3+4=7 & 6+1=7	3	ϩ	6
	4	⋈	1
5 th No# meets the 1 st glyph of rank 5	5	⋈	1
Total	15	Total	15

Figure.2: Key of the Pythagorean Cipher of VMS (MS-408, f.49v)

3. The underlying language of VMS (MS-408).

The fact that VMS includes twenty-eight ranks of letters refutes the claims that its underlying language might be any of those that are based on letters less than this range. The languages that are based on 28 ranks of letters are those of the countries that use Arabic or Persian script, i.e., most of the countries that were within the jurisdiction of the Islamic Caliphate during the 7th and 8th centuries CE. Today, in these countries the current used collation of letters is different from that of the ancient *Abjd* sequence. Unfortunately, by the end of the 7th century CE, *Nasr ibn Asim al-laythi*, an Arabic grammarian from Basra, changed it into *Abtṣ* sequence that still be used until today, which is based on a naïve idea, that is by placing the letters that look similar in shape beside each other²¹. He changed the collation of 26 letters excluding the first two; for instance, the letter *t* of rank 22 became the 3rd in *Abtṣ* sequence. Accordingly, his ignorance regarding the philosophy behind the sacred ranks of letters hindered the

²¹- On the change from *Abjd* to *Abtṣ* sequence by *Nasr ibn Asim al-laythi*, see Arabic Brief-Dictionary: *Al-Mu'jam Al-Wajiz* المعجم الوجيز for beginners, Ministry of Education, Cairo, 1994, p.2, at <https://archive.org/details/DRM2981/page/n11/mode/1up>

new generation of students in the countries that use the Arabic or Persian alphabets (and the equivalents in other scripts) from knowing the advantages of the collation of *Abjd* sequence and the related ancient Egyptian knowledge of the Pyramids Builders. During the following centuries, in these particular countries, and in other regions, the *Abjd* ranks remained in use only by few researchers that wanted to study in depth the intrinsic characteristics of the hidden architecture of words and sentences and the related mathematics of the celestial language.

The esoteric illustrations in VMS, particularly the spiral text in the folded page f.85v-86r, support the assumption that the creator of the cipher might was aware about the secret methods of Hermes Trismegistus and might have used the ranks of *Abjd* sequences of Sinai. In this regard, the *Abjd* sequence of Morocco²² was also taken into consideration; but all the other generated sequences based on regrouping the subsets, like the sub-ranked *Ayqgh* sequence²³ (Al-Buni, 1226, p.322), have been excluded. Hence, to test the two sequences, it was taken into account that the palaces of six letters (with ranks: 15, 18, 21, 26, 27, 28) in the sequence of Morocco are different from the original *Abjd* sequence of Sinai. Besides, in this enigmatic case, using the new *Abts* sequence of *Nasr ibn Asim al-laythi*, or any of those of regrouping the subsets particularly *Ayqgh* sequence, will never lead to identifying the underlying language of VMS; because these sequences deviate from achieving the goal of basic reckonings. Apparently, the designer of the glyphs relied on this, second, concealment trick in order to reinforce his cipher against quick decipherment by those who are not aware of the use of *Abjd* ranks in any kind of math. Besides, the change of the last stroke into a curve in the glyphs of the six letters *v*, *r*, *sh*, *t*, *z* and *z* (i.e., *Abjd* ranks 6, 20, 21, 22, 25, and 26, see table.1) represents the third concealment trick.

Using online translation portals —thanks to their services— the author then tested a selection of words from different pages of VMS (either from the text or written beside the illustrations) in order to identify its underlying language. After long process of trial and error, using Roman and Arabic keyboards, some words written in Arabic script were detected as Urdu of Hindustan (North India and Pakistan). Hindustan is the naturally rich region that was ruled by the Persians and the Arabs for many centuries prior to the Mughal reign (1526-1857 CE); and it is the region where many great philosophers and wise men were born and raised such as Pāṇini, Vishnu-Sharma, Kabir, Gandhi, and other bright names. The process of trial and error included correcting the values of what, falsely, appears in handwriting as inclined-stroke in one of the glyph cases of the letters *a*, *b*, *sh*, and *t* (i.e., *Abjd* ranks 1, 2, 21, and 22, see table.1). The change from vertical to inclined strokes in these four glyphs represents the fourth concealment trick. This work uses the glyphs of VMS in regular form, without some concealment tricks; and all glyphs were drawn by the author. The hybrid language Urdu is primarily based on using Sanskrit and Hindi words; and it includes many words borrowed from Persian and Arabic languages. The Urdu alphabet comprises 35 letters, where seven of the 28 *Abjd* ranks have two pronunciation cases (for the *Abjd* ranks 2, 3, 4, 7, 11, 20, and 22). There are also additional eleven letters compound with letter *h* of *Abjd* rank 5, which are the two cases of *Abjd* ranks 2, 3, 4, 11, and 22; and the second case of *Abjd* rank 20.

Moreover, in order to know which glyph form denotes which letter pronunciation case for each rank, the author reviewed various dictionaries of Hindustani languages such as Urdu, Pashto, Sindhi, Punjabi, Kashmiri, Hindi, Bhojpūrī, and Sanskrit; that in addition to the dictionaries of Persian and Arabic languages. Columns 11 &13 in table.1 demonstrate the equivalent Perso-Arabic and Roman letter for

²²- See the difference between the two *Abjd* sequences, *ibid*, p.2.

²³- It was created based on the use of travel-codes, where for instance, the travel-code 666 in “Revelation 13:18” is the set *w,s,kh* (6,60,600) of the 6th rank in *A,y,q,gh* sequence that is composed of sub-ranked sets (Al-Buni, 1226, p.322).

each glyph, respectively. The Urdu words of Sanskrit and Hindi origin are also written with Devanāgarī script; hence, the equivalent in Devanāgarī script is shown in column-12 in table.1. The Hindi alphabet is almost similar to the Urdu alphabet in terms of the set of single and compound letters and the *Abjd* rank(s) that each denotes. However, in Hindi, there is more than one case for *Abjd* rank 14, while there is only one case in VMS as shown in table.2; perhaps the writer excluded the other case. In Oxford's Hindi dictionary, the two letters ऋ and ॠ that both meet *Abjd* rank 14 are equal, and the first may replace the later. This process affirmed that the designer of the cipher of VMS used the original *Abjd* ranks of Sinai and the encrypted language is a medieval vernacular dialect close to the hybrid Urdu and/or Hindi of Hindustan, but with a slight difference in grammar. In addition to the excessive use of *Abjd* rank 8 "h" in prefixes of words like some vernacular Arabic dialects, where in some Arabian countries, the prefix, or auxiliary letter, *h* denotes will or shall. Using the Perso-Arabic script, many of the tested words in VMS are also found in the dictionaries of other languages of Hindustan, e.g., Sindhi, Pashto, and Punjabi. The transliteration to Devanāgarī script showed also some similarity with Bhojpūrī, Nepali, and Marathi; however, some of the words have different meanings in these other Hindustani languages—with different vowel diacritics in some cases as well— particularly in Bhojpūrī. Some parts of VMS's text seem close to Hindi, Bhojpūrī, and Nepali more than Urdu, particularly the sentences with words that include *Abjd* rank 8 "h". Online translation portals deal with some of these words in Perso-Arabic script as Pashto words (e.g., f.75r₁, table.3).

Despite the use of ranks of *Abjd* sequence, it is hard to affirm that the original text was written with Perso-Arabic script (i.e., from right to left). Perhaps VMS's text was just the output of mapping the Devanāgarī script into *Abjd* ranks, using the created glyphs. In all hypotheses, the encryption of the VMS's text with *Abjd* ranks indicates that the designer was—a descendant of—a Hindustani citizen, may be from Karachi or from the minorities of any of the Indian provinces that were using Perso-Arabic script, such as Oudh (Awadh) in Uttar Pradesh. Besides, Devanāgarī script have been designed with a condition to include at least 12 vowel-diacritics, but the Perso-Arabic script can be written and read without diacritics, similar to most of the glyphs of VMS, which may support the opinion that the original-version was written in Perso-Arabic script. However, the transliteration of few VMS glyphs to Devanāgarī script showed that each represents, or includes, a vowel diacritic such as one or two of the vertical strokes of *Abjd* rank 1 that implies *i* or *ii*= *ī*, respectively (see rank-1, table.1). It is also used instead of the first half circle in some glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 3, 4, 11 and 16 (see table.2), which denotes that each is preceded by the vowel *i*, or *i* follows the previous consonant (e.g., *bid* = pit, f.113v, table.3), but it does not appear in the writing, using Perso-Arabic script. This indicates that the original text may was written in Devanāgarī script, or the writer was aware about the two systems, because in Perso-Arabic texts the equivalent to *i* will be written as the diacritical mark "kasrah" below the letter. In this regard, there is no special glyph (or design element) in VMS for the vowel diacritics *o*, *u*, or *ū* to follow the first consonant in the words that start with, or are composed of, two consonants; they appear only in the transliterations using, e.g., Perso-Arabic or Devanāgarī script (e.g., f.1r₁, table.3). Besides, in VMS, the glyph of *Abjd* rank 6, which is the long vowel *o* or *u*, appears in most cases as the first or last letter in words (e.g., rank-6, f.14r, table.1; f.66r & f.68r₃, table.3). Similarly, in VMS, there are no special forms of glyphs for the Devanāgarī vowel diacritics *e*, *ē*, *ai*, and *m/ñ* (see, e.g., f.1r, table.3 & rank-13, f.90v, table.1).

In any case, to reduce the writing mistakes while mapping the script, or changing the direction of writing, most likely there was a second-version written in the designed glyphs as an experimental model for the final version. For an experienced scribe, the training to memorize the writing of VMS's glyphs (from the *a-t* range of 22 letters up to 35 letter-cases or more) would not take more than a week to write any text in his native language without noticeable mistakes. The scribal mistakes in writing few glyph

cases in VMS (e.g., the compound glyph of *Abjd* ranks 15,2,5 “*sabah*” (A)= to glorify God, f.1r, table.2) most likely were either a kind of grandiloquence to increase the tricks, or due to lack of concentration, and not because of forgetting the glyph form. This in itself indicates that the designer of VMS’s glyphs was a talented person. Because he not only created a system of script that is suitable for writing any language (on our planet or elsewhere) but also numerically expandable and can suit any identity in a topological way; and herein lies the essence of the mathematical linguistics of Hermes Trismegistus and the subsequent philosophers and the qualified fellows. The ancient Egyptian system of writing was also expandable²⁴. In the 80 glyphs of VMS that were reviewed so far, the only two cases that include separate vertical stroke(s) are in *Abjd* rank 21 (*sh* with one stroke) and *Abjd* rank 22 (*t* with two strokes); the rest of the cases are either the vowel *i* or $\bar{i}=ii$. The last column in table.1 shows examples of words from VMS; where each word includes the corresponding glyph (case) of the letter rank in each row, in order to show its correct identity and pronunciation. VMS’s text also includes few glyph cases that are not well written, and that give a false impression that they might be additional symbols different from the 110 glyphs that are listed in table.2.

Regarding the eleven compound letters in the Urdu or Hindi alphabets, in VMS, the only found compound glyphs are for *Abjd* rank 2 (e.g. *b* with *h* in Sanskrit words) and for *Abjd* rank 3 (e.g. *j* with *h* or *v* in Hindi or Sanskrit words). The other cases are formed by two separate glyphs. There are also other compound cases in VMS, related to words borrowed from other languages (see table.3); the most notable are that compound with *Abjd* rank 7 (e.g., *z* with *a*, *h*, or *k* in the borrowed Persian words). Besides, in Urdu or Hindi, the words that start with the *Abjd* ranks 8, 9, 16, 19, and from 23 to 28 are mostly borrowed from Persian or Arabic languages; hence, in few cases in VMS, if they are not included in the reviewed Urdu, Hindi, or Hindustani dictionaries, they are included either in the Persian or Arabic dictionary.

Furthermore, the scribes omitted the spaces between some words in VMS; e.g., between the pronouns (I, we, he, she, it), negative words (e.g., no, not), or definite article (e.g., a, the), and the following word, where each became a prefix of other words (e.g. f.1r₁, f.7r₁, and f.90v, table.3). In some cases, this led to the repeat of the letter *a*, three or four times, in two attached words (e.g., f.3v, f.7r₂, & f.115r₁, table.3). Besides, in some cases, the scribes also detached the suffix, or the last letter, of some words and used each as a prefix for the next word (e.g., f.10v₃, table.3). These actions formed the fifth concealment trick. Regarding the used Urdu, Hindi, and Sanskrit pronounces in VMS, the pronouns *tū* तू and *tum* तुम that both means “you”, for singular and plural, respectively, are not used; perhaps because the letter *t* of rank 22 is rarely used at the beginning of words. Alternatively, in VMS, the pronouns *āp* for respect (e.g., rank-2, f.53r, table.1) and *yo* (e.g., rank-6, f.14r, table.1) are used for both singular and plural. The pronoun *ham* that means “we” or “I” (e.g., rank-5, f.1r, table.1), and the pronoun *maiñ* (e.g. f.90v, table.3) or *zah* (e.g., rank-7, f.1r, table.1) that both means “I” are used in the text, where *zah* (in vernacular dialects) was used in an excessive way in the second half of VMS. Besides, the pronouns *yah* (e.g., rank-6, f.1r, table.1) and *so* (e.g., rank-15, f.42r, table.1) that both means “he, she, or it” are used in the text. This group of pronouns, definite article, and negative words (e.g. *na*, rank-14, f.22r, table.1) together represent the fingerprint of both Urdu and Hindi languages. Some of them, but not all together, are also used in other Hindustani languages; for instance, *zah* (originally Persian ز) is used

²⁴- The original idea of the Egyptian Hieroglyphs could be used with any tongue too, based on using the first letter of the name of the drawn inanimate thing or live creature —excluding humans— as the letter that glyph denotes, see (Aboulfotouh, 2017). For instance, using the English tongue, the glyphs of television or tower denote the letter *t*, and the glyphs of camera or cat denote the letter *c*, and so on.

in Pashto to denote “I”. In addition, some of the Bhojpūrī pronouns are like that of Hindi and Urdu, such as *ham* and *tū*.

Moreover, the sixth concealment trick is that the designer created special glyphs for the first letters of the borrowed Persian, Arabic, and Sanskrit words with special accent that are not frequently used, while he kept the same rank of each as is; which increased the number of Glyphs. The seventh concealment trick is that in all the words that end with the second and third cases of *Abjd* rank 1 (*ā* and *u* in table.1), the scribe wrote it above the letter that precedes it in the word in order to give a false impression that it is a kind of vowel-diacritics (e.g., f.8r, table.3). Excluding the last *Abjd* rank 1 in any word, in most of the reviewed cases, the sequence of reading all the compound glyphs or terms in VMS is as follows: (i) top-down, (ii) from left to right, and (iii) cover before core. Additionally, Urdu and Hindi languages include abbreviated words that each forms a prefix of other a long word and both have the same meaning (e.g., f.r₂ & f.116r₁, table.3).

Many of the reviewed words in VMS are classified as special dialect in “Urdu, Classical Hindi, and English Dictionary” by John T. Pllatts (1884), which was the best available to the author in this regard. It was noticed too that the transliteration of some easy sentences (mainly Indian words) using the Devanāgarī script could be translated online as Hindi, Bhojpūrī, Nepali, and Marathi too, but with a slight difference from the Urdu meaning based on using the Perso-Arabic script. The case is also similar when transliterating these sentences using Gujarātī script. Besides, some reviewed words and few sentences in Perso-Arabic script were translated online as Sindhi or Pashto. The reason is that Hindustani languages share a large number of colloquial words. This work used only the spelling and the meanings of Hindi and Sanskrit words with Devanāgarī and Roman script that are found in Pllatts’ Urdu Hindi dictionary or Oxford’s Hindi dictionary. The spellings in Devanāgarī script for the borrowed Arabic and Persian words are not included in Pllatts’ dictionary, but were either available online or were done by the author, and their meanings are those found in the Persian-English dictionary by Steingass (1892) and/or the Arabic-Arabic dictionary by Firuzabadi the Persian scholar (1329-1414CE).

4. The subject of VMS (MS-408).

After transliterating the selected sentences, the author searched on the meaning of each word in those sentences in the dictionaries of the Hindustani languages (e.g., Urdu, Hindi, Sanskrit, Bhojpūrī, Sindhi, Pashto, Punjabi, and Nepali) that were mostly published in the 19th and early 20th centuries, as well as in Persian and Arabic dictionaries. The author also reviewed the grammar of Urdu and Hindi languages in order to be able to detach the attached words or letters in VMS’s text, e.g., with pronouns, prepositions, negative words, and/or definite articles. The grammar of Pashto language was also reviewed because some words in VMS end with suffixes similar to that in Pashto words. The method of generating words from a root in Sanskrit was reviewed as well. Taking into consideration that each word may have diverse meanings related to the context of use, this process just gives a general idea about the possible scenarios of what each sentence might say, even if it was just a representation of celestial codes (system-code and travel-code). The processing of each of these sentences in more than two online translation sites, using Perso-Arabic or Devanāgarī script, not all ways give the correct meanings of all words in the sentence as mentioned in the dictionaries. As noticed in this particular case, machine-learning translators use modern and formal meanings of some Hindustani words. In some cases, which may indicate a design defect, these online systems give the meanings of the nearest spellings of the transliterated words.

Before reaching any conclusion regarding any transliterated sentence, the author asked many Hindustanis to read or hear each sentence. Fortunately, in the city where the author lives, there are foreigners from Indian, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Nepal who live and work there too. The interviewed persons speak Urdu, Hindi, Bhojpūrī, Pashto, and/or Nepali. Some of them are university professors, post-graduate students, medical doctors, engineers, and/or labors, where all have direct contact with the author by virtue of the work in the university campus. This in addition to those who work in diverse jobs in the city to provide services for the public, such as taxi-drivers, sellers, tailors, technicians, etc., and some of them completed their studies until high school. Hence, they formed a rich and diversified sample of public-opinions throughout the process of testing and improving the transliteration and translation of the selected sentences from VMS, particularly after discovering the last three concealment tricks —from the 5th to the 7th— that concern the underlying language. The interviewed persons saw only the transliterated text written in either Perso-Arabic or Devanāgarī script; they were informed that it is research on an old Hindustani text, which was written in a way similar to the ancient Egyptian Hieratic. No questionnaire was used in this process; it was just a talk. Some of them have also listened to the provided audio reading of sample sentences by the online translation sites. Regarding whether VMS's text includes spiritual sentences —of ideal-codes— or not, it is outside the scope of this work.

Box.1: Translation of the last sentence in VMS (MS-408, f.116v)

बक हक दाव (दाव)

bak hak daāv (daāāv)

बक हक दाव (दाव)

بک ہک داؤ (داؤ)

Chat on shocking tricks

or

buk hak daāv (daāāv)

बुक हक दाव (दाव)

بُک ہک داؤ (داؤ)

Diary of shocking tricks

Unfortunately, the title page of VMS is missing, but the short sentence in the last page (f.116v) is transliterated as shown in box-1. In Pillates's Urdu-Hindi dictionary, *bak* means idle talk, chatter, silly talk, or nonsense; it is mentioned in the introductory page and in many sentences in VMS (f.r1₂, table.3); in Sindhi, it means chatter too; but in Sanskrit, it means heron and the two letters बक are written as *baka* in Roman script. Besides, in Urdu, *hak* means shocked or stunned and *daāāv* means tricks or plans of chess; hence, it could be “chat on shocking tricks”. The word *daāāv (daāv)* —originally Sanskrit— is mentioned many times in VMS too. An Indian faculty member and colleague, who speaks Urdu and Bhojpūrī too, said the vernacular meaning of the sentence is “nonsense on dirty tricks”, which may support the assumption that there might be a deceptive goal. However, it seems illogical that any qualified fellow of Hermes Trismegistes's school of architectonic philosophy drifts to the deception corridor without an intention to achieve any public benefit at such specific point in time. On the other hand, in Urdu-Arabic dictionary, the word “*buk*” with *damma* (vowel *u*) on the first consonant means “book”, “notebook”, or “diary”, and “*bak bak*” means “chatter” (f.115v, table.3). Hence, the sentence could be “diary of the shocking tricks”. Online translation says, “claim the right to the book”, which is too far from the true meaning, because it translates *hak* हक as *haq* हक —originally Arabic— that means “the right”. Anyway, this gives an idea regarding what is in our hands includes some tricks and nonsense; however, in modern times, “nonsense” has become the title of some works that critics deal with as containing valuable arts. Hence, excluding the word “dirty”, the first two meanings of the sentence could be valid, as shown in box.1.

5. The production team of VMS (MS-408).

In many pages of VMS, starting from f.55r, the writer says “I am Abyssinian” *zah habash* (e.g., f.75r, table.3). It could be a metaphor, which means a person with a dark skin. Alternatively, perhaps he refers to one of the Siddi ethnic minorities in Hindustan, the descendants of the eastern African soldiers, particularly from Ethiopia, who came to Hindustan during the Arab conquests in 712 CE and during later periods (see, e.g., Basu, 2001 & Lodhi, 1992). Urdu or Hindi became one of their languages, and now some of them are Christians or Hindus. The writer also says, I am Habat “*zah habat*” (f.55v₂, table.3). If *h* is not an auxiliary letter before *but*, i.e., *h but*, the word *habat* may refer to a person from Habatpur village in Uttar Pradesh. According to Encyclopedia of the Arabs, the *Habatiun* were ethnic Arab groups immigrated to Sindh in Hindustan (Al-Bustani, 1887, Vol.10, p.112). In Firuzabadi dictionary, *Habat* is referenced to *Habaty* tribal group in Iraq, and may be related to mountain Habton in Mocul. In the same page the writer says I am irrevocably divorced “*zah mobit*”(f.55v₃, table.3), which may imply a Muslim women because it occurs in Muslim traditions; it also occurs in Hindu traditions only after separation for seven years. Regarding their characters and professions, one of them says, my hair is shaved or braided “*zah mū*” (f.28v, table.3), and another one says, I am a snakes’ collector or magician “*zah haw*” (f.75r₂, table.3). Other woman says, I am a flowering shrub “*zah ye bush*” as a metaphor, and I am coughing “*zah ah*” (f.115_{2&3}, table.3). In the last paragraph of VMS, the Abyssinian says, in borrowed Persian-Arabic words —if *h* is not an auxiliary letter— I am a pulsator “*zah habaz*” may be in creativity or as an activist, and I am a knitter “*zah habak*” may be in writing (f.116_{3&4}, table.3). The writers, or the characters in the chatter, mentioned their other epithets in the text (see, e.g., f.17v₂, f.54v, & f.58r, & f.75v₂, table.3).

If those Hindustanis were speaking about themselves, it implies they were a team of writers, scribes, and painters; and at least one of them was a woman, and perhaps one of them too was the designer of the cipher. The full translation of VMS may reveal that what is in our hand could be a kind of biography or diary of some nomadic tribes emigrated from Hindustan to Europe during the pre-Renaissance period. It is worth mentioning here that, in VMS, the writer referred to himself as Zott or Zatt the victorious (f.51v, table.3). Zott are one of the tribes of Gypsies —like Romani and Dom— who had emigrated from Hindustan to Persia, Iraq, Turkey, Armenia, Levant, Egypt, Crete, Greece, and Romania between the 7th and 14th centuries CE; they were musicians, dancers, palm readers, or blacksmiths. A group of them emigrated to France and Germany during the second decade of the 15th century CE; see articles in UNESCO Courier (Glissant Ed. & *et al*, 1984, pp.1-34). Some of them either men or women —the so-called Roma— were captivated in Romania in the middle of the 14th century and became slaves there for several decades (Achim, 1998). Their ways of life and migrations to different countries in the world during the last six centuries are full of exciting stories and events, which inspired many writers, artists, and musicians in their creative works. The Gypsies in general were and still are speaking some vernacular Hindustani dialects (e.g., Sanskrit, Hindi, Marathi, and Nepali) but have no writing script and have no consistent grammar. In Hindustan, particularly in Uttar Pradesh, the lower social classes among them are called the nomadic Lohars that their men usually work as blacksmiths. One of the interviewed persons from Karachi in Pakistan, who speak Urdu and Pashto, said the nomadic people who live in the outskirts of Karachi (of Sindh) speak vernacular dialects that have no grammar and use words borrowed from many languages in Hindustan. According to Al-Bustani (1887, Vol.9, p.223), “Zutt are tribal group from Sindh who were musicians and dancers; and based on citing Ibn Khaldun, they had emigrated to Basra in Iraq during, or before, the 7th century CE and participated in the battle of Camel with the Imam Ali in 656 CE. From 810 to 835 CE, they organized a rebellion against Al-Ma’mun and his son, in south Iraq, and in 838 CE, they joined the army of Al-Mu’tasim and settled in his camp in Ain Zarba (Anazarbus in little Armenia, in Turkey) but their men (14 thousand) were killed

in a Roman raid and their women (13 thousand) were captivated”. Currently, the educated Zott/Zutt people (or Jats²⁵) have reached high position in India and Pakistan; and some educated Zott migrants have become celebrities in other countries in the Middle East and in other countries in the world. Fortunately, the Gypsies have now an International Union²⁶ affiliated with the United Nations²⁷.

Now, with an acceptable degree of credibility, we can say that VMS was produced by some educated persons from the Zott immigrants, and perhaps it was in collaboration —with other persons from other nomadic Gypsies or— with some European natives. The question that arises here is, where these Zott writers studied —was it there in their country of origin or in the countries to which they immigrated? If we searched the internet to see how the Indian or Persian nomadic shepherds live, cook, and lead their cattle in the pastures, one of the scenes that will inspire the artist to imitate it in his paintings is how they bathe in a large stone basin, temporarily constructed on a water stream, similar to that portrayed in VMS. We will find as well the white rare goat that has three breasts and long ear.

As have been mentioned herein above, the schematic map in the folded page f.85v-86r indicates that there was an architect in the team, and perhaps he created the cipher too. The level of artistic accuracy of drawing the bodies of humans and animals in VMS’s illustrations are similar to the low-quality sketches that are usually produced by some students of architecture —in our faculties of fine arts— because they did not study the anatomy and the motion of bodies like students in the department of graphics or paintings. If the architect was not from Hindustan, maybe he was someone like the Italian architect and polymaths Leon Battista Alberti (1404-1472 CE) who invented one of the poly-alphabetic ciphers in 1467 CE. In this regard, in an invited conversation at academia.edu (in November 2017) about a publication by Plofker *et al* (2017) regarding the dispute about dating the Bakhshālī manuscript from Hindustan (Kumari, 1979), Aboulfotouh (2017b) explained how the Bakhshālī numerals from 1 to 9 were created by the method of “design by addition”. It showed that the assembling elements of the Bakhshālī numerals are parts of the circumference of the circle and its radius, which is closely related to Archimedes theorem on the circle (Heath, 1897, pp.91-92). The designer of the cipher of VMS may was also from Hindustan, and the cipher may have been designed long before the days of using it in encrypting the text of VMS. It is strange that VMS is the only found book written in this way, which leads to thinking about the reason that prevented these people from producing other copies or similar works, using the same set of glyphs. One of the hypotheses is that they were captivated and killed during one of the doctrinal disorders —such as the Taborites war— and all their works were burned, but fortunately, for some reason, VMS was the only book that survived the fire, similar to the case of Dresden and Madrid codices of the Maya in Guatemala. May be the caldron played its part for protecting this book, and probably, its trip from a private library to another was not a coincidence. Perhaps it is the oldest book of the Gypsies, and even if it was nothing more than a funny gossip, it will represent a great heritage fortune for them, at least the created glyphs.

Moreover, regarding the origin of the mathematical notion of the Expandable Geometric Substitution Cipher, there is a claim that the Pythagorean philosophy (see Pedersen, 1993, pp.16-20) and theorem were similar to that of *Sulvasutra* geometers who were aware about Pythagoras theorem long before his days, where the earliest was that of Baudhāyana, dating back to 800 BCE (Dani, 2011). In this regard, a Renaissance writer did argue that Pythagoras did not visit India but the Pythagorean books may were

²⁵- See Wikipedia page on Jats (<https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jats>).

²⁶- The “International Romani Union” was established in 1971 (www.iru2020.org).

²⁷- During the United Nations’ General Assembly in July 14, 2014, the Human Right Resolution A/HRC/RES/26/4 was issued on the protection of the vulnerable Roma and Gypsies everywhere in the world, which followed the Human Right Resolution 1992/65.

carried into India (Della Valle, 1664, p.76). In the Egyptian history, Pythagoras was admitted as a Piromis²⁸ (like a brilliant research-fellow) in the temple of Heliopolis after passing the three required exams in three temples: Sais, Memphis, and Heliopolis (Al-Maqrizi, 1364–1442CE, Heliopolis sec.). His scientific prowess has enabled him to promote to the highest priestly ranks in Ancient Egypt; but he left Egypt during the Persian reign. As known, Egypt and Hindustan were part of the Persian (539-330BCE) and Hellenistic (323-32 BCE) empires, hence, the dissemination of information about the use of geometric methods in designing numeric signs by addition may be happened during those eras or during later periods. In any case, the ancient Egyptian triangles 3-4-5 and 6-8-10 and the related mathematical applications of glyph designs are both found in Rhind Mathematical Papyrus that goes back to the days of the Pyramids Builders (Aboulfotouh 2012, 2019, 2022). The dissemination of the ancient Egyptian mathematical knowledge and the architectonic philosophy of Hermes Trismegistus by any means had enabled the designer of the cipher and led him to use the triangle 6-8-10 and the idea of “design by addition”. The created forms of glyphs and the related knowledge as well as the technique of handwriting indicate that he might have studied in several countries, such as Hindustan, Persia, Egypt, Greece, and may be in other countries in Europe. Perhaps he was traveling between countries to search for knowledge and not —only— as a musician or a blacksmith that search for a job opportunity; and maybe he was the leader of the Gypsies at that time, the so-called Duke of the district of little Egypt in Greece.

Now in the light of knowing who wrote VMS, we can analyze and understand the design morphology and symbolism in the schematic map in the folded page f.85v-86r. The designer did it in the form of an abstract model like the one that architects and planners use to analyze the proximity of design or planning entities. It groups nine geographic regions, cities, or holy places in different countries, where the entity in the middle demonstrates a holy place in Hindustan; maybe temples of Jainism or Buddhism in Uttar Pradesh (maybe in Varanasi the city of Kabir). Metaphysically, the designer used one of the distorted transformation forms of the topological celestial communication matrix²⁹ 3*3 —of the 12th *Abjd* rank ¹²*l*₃₀— as a base for this geographic scheme as follows:

	11	6	13		6	13	11
Original matrix ³⁰	12	10	8	Transformed matrix in VMS	8	12	10
	7	14	9		9	7	14

In page f.85v-86r, the designer drew what represents the numbers 13 and 7 in the middle column in blue color. Despite that, this partial catastrophic transformation —by the effect of 3 independent horizontal movements or rotations— distorted the total sum 30 of rows and columns; it placed the clock of 12 hours in the middle of the scheme, together with the other intervals of time in our planet —7 days and 13 years— in the middle column. The drawing of a castle with European architecture style in the southern entity (number 11) indicates that the designer rotated the coordinates 180° —perhaps as a

²⁸- Piromis πῖρωμις is the title of young priests in ancient Egypt (Herodotus, 484-425 BCE, pp.450-451); which is below the High Priest(s), the so-called *Qutter* “the leader” who received seven scientific certificates in multi-disciplinary ancient sciences (Al-Maqrizi, 1364–1442 CE).

²⁹- In abstract mathematics, it is called “Magic Square” denoting incomprehensible effect, and in medieval books, it was called the “Ring” denoting the effect of rotation and travel in space-time.

³⁰- The original matrix was highlighted in Mesopotamia (Iraq) in a famous book written at the end of the 7th century, which was also written on parchments made of goatskin; it is the so-called *Kitab al-Jafr* written by Shia Imam. It tells the events of the end of the world in a set of Arabic verses. See the matrix in page 102 in *Kitab al-Jafr* at (https://archive.org/details/20191106_20191106_2315/page/n51/mode/1up).

concealment trick— where north became south, while east (6) and west (14) remained as is. The scheme records nine places that the writers visited, emigrated to them, or knew them well.

Figure.3: The geographic entities in the transformed celestial matrix of the letter $^{12}L_{30}$ in VMS (MS-408, f.85v-86r).

As shown in fig.3, the three circular entities —like horizons— in the top row represent Xinjiang Uygur “6”, Armenia or little-Armenia in Turkey “13”, Methoni *Μεθώνη* castle port and village (in Greece) “11”. The main camp of the Gypsies —the so-called little Egypt— was in Medon, i.e., Methoni (De Foletier, 1984, UNESCO Courier, p.6). The V shapes of the battlement wall (Swallowtail Merlons) at the top of the watchtower (36°48'42"N 21°42'17"E) by the gate of Methoni castle is still there. The V shapes of the battlement wall of Methoni Castle also appear in the artwork “Young Night in a Landscape” by the Italian painter Vittore Carpaccio³¹ in about 1500 CE. In the road between Turkey/Armenia “13” and Xinjiang Uygur “6”, the designer drew a tower, which might be the minaret tower of Manuchihr Mosque (Ebul Menuçehr Camii); it is located in a mountainous area in Armenia’s western border with Turkey (40°30'20"N 43°34'12"E). The sundial in the horizon of “13” is most likely related to Armenia more than Turkey; but the road between Methoni and Turkey or Armenia shows what looks like the Constantinople walls, which is also close to Sulukule, the old district of the Romani gypsies in Turkey. The other hypothesis is the medieval walls and towers in the mountainous area of Ain Zarba in little Armenia in Turkey. The three circular horizons in the middle row represent Tibet “8”, a holy place in Hindustan (in India or Pakistan) “12”, and Sinai or Nile delta (in Egypt) “10”. In the central horizon “12”, the scribe wrote God “*Dev*” above the temples' lake (f.85v-f.86r, table-3). The three circular horizons in the third row represent Thailand and/or Malaysia “9”, Horn of Africa “7”, and the Sacred Mosque and Kaaba in Makkah, Madinah Mosque, and Jeddah port (in Saudi Arabia) “14”. The designer also drew a small entity representing Crete in the road between Egypt “10” and Greece “11”. Besides, in the horizon of the Sacred Mosque in Makkah “14” —and other entities— he drew what represent the flow of the pilgrims from other regions and the rows of worshippers in Madinah Mosque in the form of adjacent arches. The scheme demonstrates two volcanoes, one in Greece “11” (Methana *Μέθανα* Volcano) and the other maybe in Al-Abwa or Wadi Al-Fora’a in Makkah region in KSA “14”. It shows as well a Tornado in the horizon of Thailand “9”. Regarding the use of cylinders,

³¹- Art historian “Augusto Gentili” identified the place in the artwork “Young Night in a Landscape” as Methoni Castle; see <https://www.museothyssen.org/en/collection/artists/carpaccio-vittore/young-knight-landscape>

the 5 vertical cylinders —the rotated in the projection plan— at the edge of the horizon of Xinjiang Uygur "6" indicates that number six is five levels above one, in the celestial matrix from one to nine. The 12 groups of six cylinders at the edge of the horizon of Hindustan "12" may be related to the six eternal substances and the six divisions in the two sides of the cosmic wheel of time in the philosophy of Jainism. In the horizon of Tibet "8", the designer did not draw what represents eight, but instead he drew what represents nine in yellow color, which may refer to the nine vehicles of the mind according to the philosophy of Nyingma School in Buddhism.

The schematic map hints to that, in the mind of VMS's writers (e.g., Zott or Jats), the executive objective might be they wanted to write about themselves and their journey across the regions, and to describe and depict their living conditions, their nomadic life, their historic narratives, and what they believe in with symbolic or surreal sketches. In these sketches, the artistic way to draw people's foreheads with noses, four fingers in each hand, sun, stars, and the zigzagged boundaries as well as the color scheme used in VMS are very much similar to the work of the German painter Johann Bämle from Augsburg (1430-1503 CE) in the 3rd illustrated edition of *Buch der Natur*³² (1481 CE). He was also a scribe and owner of a printing office. If VMS was produced by Johann Bämle or his elder employees —from Zott, Dom, or Romani emigrants— this may partly explain how it reached the hand of the known botanist Leonhard Rauwolf (1535-1596CE). Then as Guzy (2022) pointed out, it was inherited to the physician Karl Widemann who lived in Rauwolf's house in Augsburg and sold some manuscripts from Rauwolf's library to Rudolf II. The trip of Rauwolf to Mosul in Iraq and other places in Mesopotamia (in 1574) may point to that perhaps he heard some stories about the region from which the Zott producers of the manuscript might have immigrated to his city, and he wanted to investigate the origin of the portrayed plants in that region.

6. The social benefit of VMS (MS-408).

VMS, as a cultural heritage, has now additional social benefit, which is not only the used chipper method and the relevant math but also the future use of its set of 80 glyphs by the grandsons of its producers that many of them live now in a diaspora in various countries in the world. It may represent as well a public benefit to their homeland. Despite the use of many glyph forms for each *Abjd* rank added additional complexity, which may be unnecessary, the author admires the mindset and the creativity of the designer and his additional seven tricks. It is a magical idea that many great minds will think about its merits, consequences, and benefits for many years to come. The first direct return, based on the results of this work, is that transliterating and publishing the full translation of VMS has now become possible. All researchers from north India and Pakistan or those who are specialized in the Hindustani languages —with the use of table.1 and table.2 in this work— will be able to read the full text of VMS without transliteration. For the rest of the scientific community and those who are interested in the subject including the author of this work, the full translation of VMS will answer many questions. For instance, was it worth the efforts of many experts, researchers, and scholars during several decades and even centuries ago? Does it include some valuable lessons, traditions, and/or philosophies written by a humorous writer like Vishnu Sharma the author of *Panchatantra* (Fables of Pilpay), some of Kabir's poems, legendary tales about Gev, or some health advices like those of Gandhi in "the Key to Health"? Alternatively, was it a competition, hidden in a deceptive nonsense text, to decode the Pythagorean cipher and to discover the seven concealment tricks via reviving part of the philosophy of our great Architectonic master "Hermes Trismegistus", as one of the ancient secret sciences of the Pyramids Builders? Above all, despite of the accumulated socio-economic costs, some

³²- See his works at (https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Johann_Bämle).

financial loss, and the agony in searching for the truth during almost six centuries, some may see that it still has a live and noble goal for the current and future generations of the people that it represents and narrates about them. In any case, the author of this work is not a direct beneficiary in this regard, but he is only a passerby in the land of lost knowledge.

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 - f- Janush, R. The sharing, caring family
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 - h- Novitch, M. Half a million Gypsies victims of the Nazi terror
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Table.1: The glyphs of VMS (MS-408) and their equivalents in Persian, Devanāgarī, and Roman script, and examples of words from its text. *

Abjd rank	Glyph used in VMS	Numeric values of the assembling parts of the glyphs used in VMS (MS-408)								Pronunciation of the glyph letters: (P/A) Perso-Arabic, (H) Hindi (in Devanāgarī), & (R) Roman			Examples of words from VMS, with Perso-Arabic & Hindi transliterations, Roman pronunciation with vowels, and English meaning. Symbols of languages or origin of words: Hindi (H), Persian (P), Arabic (A), Sanskrit (S), & Pashto (Psh)
		1	1	1	1	1	5	10	10	P/A	H	R	
		۱	۱	۱	۱	۱	۵	۱۰	۱۰				
1	۱		1							آ/ا	अ/ा	ā	آآآ ۱آآ (H)= self, elder sister (f.7v).
	۲	1							ا	उ	u	۲ا ۱آ (S) = on, under, by, proximity (f.4r).	
	۳			1					آ/ا	अ	ā	آآ ۱آ (P) = lime, cement, plaster, cement (f.3r)	
	۴				1				ا	इ/ि	i	۲ا ۱آ (H) = pub (f.100r)	
2	۵		1		1				ب	ब	b	آ ۱آ (S/H) = idle talk, chatter, nonsense (f.1r).	
	۶	1	1						پ	प	p	آآ ۱آ (S/H) = you for respect (f.53r). ۲ ۱آ (S/H) = drink, air, God of the wind, protect, five; and it is also used before verbs to assert the action, and as prefix or suffix of words (f.9r); and ۲ ۱آ (Psh) = by, with.	
	۷	2							ب	ब	b	۳ ۱آ (P/A) = by, with, in, for (f.10r)	
	۸		1			1			ب (with h=अ)	ब	b	۱آ ۱آ (S) = life, origin, world (f.15v).	
3	۹		1	1		1			ج	ज	j	۱آ ۱آ (S/H) = who, what, which, if (f.1r).	
	۱۰		2			1			ح	च	č/ch	۱آ ۱آ (H) = wish (f.66r).	
4	۱۱		2	1		1			د	द	d	۱آ ۱آ (H)= inflamed, burning (f.88v).	

13				2	1	2*5			م	म	m	 mach مجھ मछ (H)= fish (f.8r); main میں मैं (H) = I, egotism (f.90v).
			3	2	3	5			م	म	m	 mah مہ मह (P) = great (f.1r).
14				2	2	2*5			ن	न	n	 na ننه (H) = nahin نہیں नीं (H) = no, not, nor (f.22r).
15			1	2	2	2*5			س	स	s	 is اس इस (H)= this (f.8r)
			1	2	2	2*5			س	स	s	 so سو सो (H) = he, she, it, that, so, so that, hence (f.42r); if the 1 st glyph is the combined <i>bm</i> بم बम (H) = water spring; then, the 2 nd glyph <i>wa</i> व (P/A) = also, and.
16			2	2	2	2*5			ع	अ/,	ā/,	 abak عبك अबक (A) = mix things (f.8r)
17			2	2	3	2*5			ف	फ	f	 faw فاو फाव (P/A) = striking (f.7r).
18			3	2	3	2*5			ص	स	s	 sahak صهك सहक (A) = top of, saddle's position on the horse's back (f.1r).
19			4	2	3	2*5			ق	क	q	 qaaw قاو काव (A) = few rain, lake of food, empty place, hungry man (f.80r).
20	∨						10	10	ر	र	r	 bar بر बर (H) = choosing, but, moreover, Indian fig tree (f.36r).
	⊗					2*5	10		ڑ	ड	r	 cār چار चाड़ (H)= mark, love (f.66r).
21	∨			1			10	10	ش	श or ष	sh	 habash حبش हबश (A) = Abyssinian, or a black man (f.75r).
	⋈				1		10	10	ش	श or ष	sh	 shabak شبك शबक (A) = nets, lattice, to make reticulated (f.55r).
22	∨			2			10	10	ت	त	t	 ye but ي بت ये बुत (H) = the idol (f.1r).
			1	3	3	3*5			ت	त	t	 tuca تُچا तुचा = luca लुचा (H) = low, bad, base (f.100v-101r).

	ख				1	1		10	10	ٹ	ट	t	ख caṭ چٹ चट (H)= quickly, a sound, wholly, eating up (f.66r).
23	स				4	4	3*5			स	स	ṣ	स śacāv सचआव (H/P) = the truth (f.87v).
24	ख		2		3	4	3*5			ख	ख	kh	ख kho خو खو or khuu खू (P) = nature, way, custom (f.86v).
25	ज						5	10	10	ज	ज	z	ज baḷ बज (P/A) = victory (f.65r).
26	ज				1		5	10	10	ज	ज	z	ज baḷ بض बज (P/A) = sick, lanky, or skinny concubine (f.65r).
27	घ				4	3	4*5			घ	घ	z	घ it appeared as a standalone letter in one diagram (f.57v).
28	घ		4		4	5	3*5			घ	घ/ग	gh/g	घ gaib/ghaib غيب गैब (A)= unseen, absent, invisibility (f.90r).

* In this work, the used font of VMS’s glyphs is regular, with omitting some concealment tricks, that are: (i) the inclination of the vertical stroke in the letters *sh* & *t*, and what denotes the vowels *i* and *ii=ī*; (ii) the end curves in the letters *v*, *r*, *ṣ*, *sh*, *t*, *z*, & *z̄*; and (iii) the increased diameter of the upper half-circle in the letters *k* & *p*. The change that was kept as is in VMS is the reduction of the diameter of the circle from five units to one unit.

Table.2: The used Glyphs of *Abjd* ranks in VMS's text (MS-408).

<i>Abjd</i> ranks of single glyphs			
1	2	3	4
ⲉ ⲓ ⲏ ⲓ	ⲏ ⲓ ⲓ ⲉ ⲓ ⲉ	ⲉ ⲉ ⲉ ⲉ	ⲉ ⲉ ⲉ ⲉ
5	6	7	8
ⲟ	ⲑ ⲑ	ⲑ ⲑ ⲓ	ⲑⲑ
9	10	11	12
ⲑⲑ	ⲓ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲓ ⲓ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲉ
13	14	15	16
ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ
17	18	19	20
ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲉ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲓ ⲓ ⲓ
21	22	23	24
ⲓ ⲓ ⲓ	ⲓ ⲓ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲓ	ⲑⲑ
25	26	27	28
ⲓ	ⲓ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ
<i>Abjd</i> ranks of samples of compound glyphs			
1,1,7	1,2	2,1	2,5
ⲉⲑ	ⲉ	ⲉ	ⲉ ⲉ
2,25	3,1	3,5	3,6
ⲉⲓ	ⲉⲓ	ⲉⲓ	ⲉⲓ
3,17 (or 19)	6,1	7,1	7,5
ⲉⲑⲑ	ⲉ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
7,6	7,5,1	8,7,1	9,7 (or 7,9)
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
10,2 (or 2,7,3)	10,1 (or 8,2,1)	10,6 (or 8,2,6)	11,1,7
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲉⲑ
12,2 (or 13)	15,5 (or 13,2,5)	15,6 (or 13,2,6)	15,2,5
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
16,2 (or 17)	17,2 (or 18)	22,1	28,4 (or 4, 28)
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲓ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ

f.51r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Persian/ Hindi	گاو	<i>gā'o = gāv</i>	गाव	Bull, ox, or cow
f.51v	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi/ Persian	زط بڙ (جٹ بڙ)	<i>zatt baz (jatt baz)</i>	ज़ट्ट बज़ (जट्ट बज़)	Zatt the victorious (Zatt/Jatt is a tribe from Hindustani)
f.53r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Arabic	نہی	<i>nahy</i>	नहय	Prohibition, forbidding
f.55v ₁	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Sanskrit	بر	<i>bari</i>	बीर	bury
f.54v	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Pashto	Hindi/ Pashto	زه مچو	<i>zah ma'cu</i>	ज़ेह मचो	I am careless, flying, a mosquito
f.55v ₂	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Arabic/ Persian	زه حبت	<i>zah ḥabat</i>	ज़ेह हबत	I am Habatinian (الحبثيون Arabs of Sindh, may be from Mosul in Iraq)
f.55v ₃	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Arabic/ Persian	زه مېت	<i>zah Mobit</i>	ज़ेह मोबित	I am irrevocably divorced
f.58r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	زه نبيض	<i>zah nabīz</i>	ज़ेह नबीज़	I am a prophet/wise man (or I am like wine)
f.65v	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	بک	<i>bik = bīk</i>	बिक = बीक	wolf
f.66r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Arabic/ Persian	وح	<i>wah</i>	वह	Poor man, wedge
f.66r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	کب	<i>kab</i>	कब	A poet, when?
f.68r ₁	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi/ Persian	وحو ی بکو	<i>wahu ye bakku</i>	वहू ये बककू	The poorer garrulous
f.68r ₂	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	بت بک	<i>but bak</i>	बूत बक	Idol chat
f.68r ₃	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	ڈچو = ڈچ	<i>da'coñ</i>	डचो	Dutch (may be a female)
f.68r ₄	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	یہ بکو	<i>yah bakku</i>	यह बककू	This garrulous
f.72r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Hindi/ Persian	ہم ہڈ بڙ	<i>ham haz baz</i>	हम हज़ बज़	I am a sharp lanky- concubine
f.75r ₁	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Pashto	Arabic/ Persian	زه حبش	<i>zah habash</i>	ज़ेह हबश	I am Abyssinian (the Siddi African of India), or I am a black man
f.75r ₂	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu	Arabic/ Persian	زه حاو	<i>zah ḥāw</i>	ज़ेह हाव	I am a snakes' collector/ magician
f.75v ₁	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Hindi	Hindi/ Persian	زه حايو	<i>zah ḥāyu</i>	ज़ेह हायो	I am here
f.75v ₂	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	زه نیو	<i>zah New</i>	ज़ेह नेव	I am the founder
f.78r	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	سه کبیر	<i>sah Kabir</i>	सह कबरि	With Kabir, or Kabir's village; (Kabir is the Indian mystic poet and saint)
f.78v ₁	𑂔𑂗𑂏𑂑	Urdu/ Hindi	Persian	سو حايو	<i>Su ḥāyu</i>	सू हायो	Come to fountain Su (in Tūs, Iran)

f.78v ₂	دایو	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi/ Sanskrit	دایو	<i>dāyu</i>	दायो	give
f.85v- f.86r	دیو	Urdu	Hindi/ Sanskrit	دیو	<i>dev</i>	देव	Deity, God, temple of God, divinity
f.90v	میں دھپ	Urdu	Hindi	میں دھپ	<i>main dhap</i>	में धप	I loss, or I blow
f.113r	زه مبار	Urdu/ Pashto	Arabic/ Persian	زه مبار	<i>zah mubār</i>	ज़ेह मुबार	I am pudding, sausage
f.113v	बिद	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	बिद	<i>bid</i>	बिद	a pit into which children in play endeavor to throw balls or marbles
f.115r ₁	हा आप	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	با آپ	<i>hā āp</i>	हा आप	Yes you
f.115r ₂	زه ی بوش	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi/ Sanskrit	زه ی بوش	<i>zah ye bush</i>	ज़ेह ये बुश	I am a shrub
f.115r ₃	زه اح	Urdu	Arabic/ Persian	زه اح	<i>zah āḥ</i>	ज़ेह अह	I am coughing
f.115v	बक बक	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	بک بک	<i>bak bak</i>	बक बक	Chatter, gossip, talk too much
f.116r ₁	दाड़ = दाढ़	Urdu/ Hindi	Hindi	داڑ = داڑھ	<i>daār=daārḥ</i>	दाड़ = दाढ़	A jaw tooth, molar
f.116r ₃	زه حبض	Urdu/ Pashto	Arabic/ Persian	زه حبض	<i>zah ḥabaz</i>	ज़ेह हबज़	I am pulsator (metaphor)
f.116r ₄	زه حېک	Urdu/ Pashto	Arabic/ Persian	زه حېک	<i>zah ḥabak</i>	ज़ेह हबक	I am the knitter (of the text)